

Urban Expansion and Wetland Destruction: A Study of Constitutional and Legal Protection of Wetland Ecosystems

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Abstract:

In Earth's total surface 71% consists of water but in that only 3% is fresh water and consumed by living things, in that overall three percent water 2% are in frozen form.¹ For the welfare of the extinction of the living things, the need for the protection of water bodies is very important for the purpose of storing drinking water. The Water Bodies play a key role in maintaining and restoring the ecological balance, support biodiversity, drinking water, control floods, recharge groundwater, and provide livelihood opportunities to a large number of people.² This paper examines the legal and constitutional safeguards relating to the wetland their protection and safety.

Keywords: Fresh water, Biodiversity, Floods, Wetlands, Groundwater.

1.0 Introduction:

"I wasn't here to make love.

I was here to make war"³ - R.K. Lilley

The quote which stated above relates in this way that I am here not to make love with the Water Bodies but I am here to make a war against the encroachment and Pollution on Water Bodies for the long life of the People. The urbanisation and unplanned growth resulted in huge floods in many of the major cities in India as we saw the huge disaster which happened in Chennai is due to the encroachment of the Water bodies.⁴

The kinds of water bodies are Ocean, Sea, Wetlands, Deltas, Lake, Rivers, Ponds; each water body has a different role in the environment. The Wetlands are useful in many ways; it acts as a sponge by observing water then purifying the water and it is useful in maintaining, supporting natural cycles and biodiversity.⁵ Lakes are used for the purpose of storing water and supply to the local people and it is also used for hydroelectric energy. For some indigenous people lakes are their livelihood and the tribal people called Uros have lived on Lake Titicaca for centuries.⁶ Every water body is used in some way for the people as well as the ecology.

Water pollution has become a major problem in the country. Water pollution is the substance which enters lakes, rivers, streams, estuaries due to this the ground water also get affected and the water which pollutes the rivers which finally reaches the ocean.⁷ In addition chemicals, microorganisms, and trash are also released in water bodies.⁸ Pollution is highly increased due to this people are forced to drink contaminated water and the United Nations estimate that by the year of 2025 , 1.8 billion people will live in areas where water is in demand.⁹ Water pollution happens in the places where the environment law is weak or the other reason is there will be sufficient water laws but the enforceability is weak or there is a lack in infrastructure. Most of the developing countries the household water is released into water courses, this leads to the death of nearly two million children below the age of five years from water-borne diseases.¹⁰

Encroachment on water bodies means the advancement of roads, structures, improved paths, railroads, utilities, and other development, into natural areas including wetlands, ponds, river corridors, floodplains, and lakes.¹¹ The State of Tamil Nadu has its encroachment law but the highest number of encroachments is also high in Tamil Nadu. There are totally 9.45 lakhs of water bodies are identified throughout the country in that 18,691 water bodies are encroached, the first census for the water bodies is conducted by Jal Shakti Ministry in their reports the highest number of encroachment is reported in the State of Tamil Nadu at 8,366 , the next is Andhra Pradesh 3,920 followed that Telangana 3,032.¹² The Madras High Court ordered to remove all the encroachments at Karadibavi Water body by April 4,2022 in this case the High Court further stated that the Government shall not give alternative land for the people those who the encroached the water body because it will encourage others to encroach the water bodies.¹³

2.0 Constitutional Perspective of Water Bodies

The mother law of the nation is Constitutional Law. The framers of the Constitution the importance of water and the environment which is indispensable to every living organism. A man is not separate with the environment both humans and environment are interdependent to form an ecology. The Constitution is expressly made provisions with regard to environment that the state and citizen have a duty to protect and improve the natural environment including forests, lakes, rivers and wild life.¹⁴ There are three list under the Constitution of India which is state list, central list and concurrent list. In every subject matter of law it will be on any one of these list and if the subject matter is not present in all the three list then the central

government has the power to make law on that subject matter.¹⁵ The seventh schedule which contain all the three list under that there are two subject matters one is on "regulation and development of interstate river"¹⁶ which is vested with the central list and the next one is "water supplies, water storage, water power, irrigation and canals, drainage and embankments these are in the State subject".¹⁷

2.0.1 Article 21

The article which evolving decade to decade and there will be a significant change. Right to Life and personal liberty¹⁸ there will be a question that what are all comes under the life and the things which included under life there is many interpretations had been given about life and what the things which included in right to life. Right to life means not only the physical existence but also the quality of life.¹⁹

2.0.1.1 Right to Life and Right to Live in Healthy Environment

Article 21 is the heart of fundamental right and has received expanded meaning from time to time and there is no justification as to why right to live in a healthy environment, cannot be interpreted in it. Ecological balance is the very important thing for healthy existence and to lead a healthy life. Article 21 guarantees a fundamental right to life with a life of dignity to be lived in a proper environment, free of danger of disease and infection. It is an established fact that there exists a close link between life and environment.²⁰

L.K. Koolwal v. State of Rajasthan²¹

The Jaipur is the capital city in the State of Rajasthan. As per the reports²² at present the population of the city of Jaipur is above forty-one lakh. This case is filed as a public interest litigation to issue a mandamus against the municipality to perform their duties. Article 51 A fundamental duties of the citizens that every citizen of India has their rights and if there is a right then there will be a duty too. These duties have enumerated under this article and particularly under article 51A(g) it is the duty of every citizen to protect and improve the natural environment.

The insanitation is the problem in this case and it leads to high medical problems to the people. The municipalities are the responsible authority to clean public streets, remove filth and all the sanitation works in the public places. Several affidavits were filed by the local

people regarding the dirty in the city. There are three duties for municipality under chapter IV of Rajasthan municipality act which are primary duty, secondary duty, special duty. Under primary duty it is the duty of the municipality to remove noxious and nuisance which is in the public place and not a private property even though the property is not vested with the board too then also the municipality will be responsible to remove the substance in public places. The municipality will not tell that there is no sufficient fund or any other thing to do their primary duties. The court has appointed a commissioner and the commissioner submitted a report stating that the municipality has taken some steps and the quantum is not reduced in that particular area. Further submitted that there is insanitation due to ties of buffalos in the road itself.²³

The court taking into consideration of the affidavits filed by the local people and several report from the bar person and report of the commissioner appointed by the court that the step takes by the municipality in very fewer places alone and still there is a huge number of insanitation is there in the city that places are not yet addressed by the municipality. The court directed the Jaipur municipality to clean the city within a period of six months and importantly to the places which was mentioned by the petitioner in this affidavit. The court states that it is not the duty of the court to find that there is sufficient fund are available or not it is the duty of the administrator, the municipal corporation is responsible.²⁴

Maintenance of health, preservation of the sanitation and environment falls under Article 21 the Constitution as it affects the life of the citizen and it amounts to slow poisoning and reducing the life of the citizen because of the hazards created. Article 51A gives right to the citizen to move Court to see that the State performs its duties faithfully and the obligatory and primary duties are performed in accordance with the law of land.²⁵

Subash Kumar v. State of Bihar²⁶

The petitioner was filed under article 32 of the constitution of India exercising the original jurisdiction of the supreme court to enforce the fundamental right of the citizen. The public interest litigation is filed to safeguard the river bokaro from discharge of untreated trade effluent which makes the river water to non-drinkable and not to use for irrigation purpose.

The petitioners alleged that the West Bokaro collieries and Tata iron and steel industry are polluting the river Bokaro by discharging their untreated trade effluent from their washeries in the way of slurry/sludge due to this discharge the water is not able to use for drinking and

irrigation purposes and causing risk for the people those who consume this poisonous water. The state pollution control board and Bihar government has not take any steps to prevent the water from the industry. Further the petitioners got the interim orders to collect the sample of sludge/slurry from the discharge of the industry in the river Bokaro and petitioner plot nearer to the river bed. The respondents' states that the petition filed by the petitioner is not in the public interest it is for his own private interest. The Bihar state pollution control board has given directions to improve the quality of the slurry. The respondents submitted that the tata iron and steel industry get permission from the state pollution control board and their level of effluents is tested and analysed frequently. On inspection it is clear that the effluent had taken into four embankments of the tanks and not discharging into river Bokaro. The slurry which discharges from the industry will store in the ponds and it is for sale because it contains highly carbonaceous materials it is used for the making of petroleum process. The petitioner is buying slurry from the respondent company for the past several years and he ask the company for more slurry, the company refused to give him more slurry he makes this writ petition to give disturbance to the company.²⁷

The court delivers that the case is not for any public interest and it is put for the petitioner personal interest so the case is dismissed and cost rupees 5000 needs to pay by the petitioner to the respondent. It is the duty of the court to discourage this kinds petition which exercise the original jurisdiction of the court in the way of public interest but it totally a person matter. From the above decision it is clear that the person will not use his powers in a wrong way to get some benefit for his personal in the way of interest of public.²⁸

3.0 Encroachment Laws on Water Bodies

"If god encroaches the public land, then the court will order the removal for that too"²⁹

- Justice N. Anand Venkatesh

The water bodies have playing an eminent role in the ecosystem and for the protection of water bodies from encroachment several Acts are enacted. In this chapter the laws related to encroachment on water bodies will be seen and what are the powers exercise by the authorities to evict the encroachers will be discussed.

3.1.1 Tamil Nadu Rivers Conservancy Act, 1884

This act is enacted for the protection of rivers in the state of Tamil Nadu from encroachments. In this act surveying officers were appointed and their duty is to make survey of the specific river and mark it in survey records and also conservator were also appointed for the purpose of doing inspections on the river and evict cultivators with the order of district collector.³⁰ This act main purpose is to prevent any thing necessary that resulted to erosion, breach of embankments or flooding of rivers.³¹

Applicability of the Act

The Tamil Nadu adoption of Law Order, 1970 has adopted this Tamil Nadu Rivers Conservancy Act, 1884³² to enforce in the state of Tamil Nadu after that there is no any Laws or Rules were made in this subject and only one amendment was made in the year 1942³³ and 1949³⁴ in this act both the amendments are minor amendments.

Surveying Officer their Powers and Duties

The State Government may time to time direct the authorities to do survey on the land for the act applied and the charts are made for the purpose of survey and land - mark boundaries will be marked as river area in the specified manner of this act.³⁵ The powers of the surveying officer is given as same as the powers which is specified under section 4 and section 5 of the Act.³⁶

The surveyor who is appointed as a surveying officer he needs to maintain record and survey the river and he needs to mention what are all things in the surveying land like plantation, construction, obstruction, any cultivating if exist or ordinarily carried upon some other things on the surveying land.³⁷ It is the duty of the surveyor to maintain that survey register and mark all the points and the particulars necessary.³⁸

Appointment of Conservator of Rivers

This Act gives the power to appoint conservator by the state government within their jurisdiction and on the said district where the river is situated and it should be published in the official gazette of the state government, if the river is situated with two jurisdictions of the different districts, then the notification made at any one of the districts is enough in this said

act. If the need of the conservator is high then the state government may appoint as many as they by their convenience.³⁹

After the complete of the survey it is duty of the district collector to put the survey records published in the said district for a period of not less than ninety days during this period the people who has any objections with the boundaries marked may raise an objection in a letter stating their grievance to the said district collector then the collector after the expiry period of ninety days record the objections from the people and mark the survey boundaries and send it to the state government then the state government shall take the objection into their record and the government may alter the record with the objections complied then the record will publish in the official gazette of the state government and in every district where the river is flowing or situated then the state government declare the said river and its boundaries will fall under this act. River-bed fixed the land which surveyed as a river is deemed to be river-bed and the boundaries is marked with stone or any other visible marks for the identification of the boundary of the area.⁴⁰

Survey Records and Charts

The custody of the survey register is given to the conservator of the specified district where the conservator is appointed with all the charts and other documents then the conservator of the district shall need to handover the certified copies of the survey register records and charts to the district collector where the said river is situated. The chart of the river is to be available for public inspection in the said district where the land is situated both the charts and registers which prepared under section 5 of this act and it is available to the public for the inspection.⁴¹

The state government at the need they will publish in the official gazette to alter, restrict, extend the size of the river and the government needs to notify in the official gazette of the state government and in the district gazette where the river boundary is situated in that district, any changes made under this provision it is the duty of the state to ask the objections from the public regarding the alteration of the size of the river, changes of size of the river is to undergo the section 7 of this act.⁴²

3.1.2 Cultivation on the River-Bed

There is a prohibition of cultivation in the notified boundaries of the river-bed which is notified in the official gazette under section 7 of the act after the survey is made and notified and the land which is notified as river-bed which not been cultivated for more than two years before when the act is applicable to the river. If the person is cultivating something in the said river, he needs to get prior permission from the conservator of the river in writing and the cultivator should not encroach any further land nearby to the cultivating land of him. The person who violates and encroaches the nearby land in the river-bed will be punished with five hundred rupees fine and if he refuses or not paid, he will send to simple imprisonment for a period of three months. The term cultivation means a land plugged once in a year or some period with the year and it should not include plantation which is mentioned under section 13 of this act.⁴³

The conservator has the power to prohibit cultivation in the river-bed , the conservator needs to get previous sanction from the district collector in writing with the cultivator or occupier name in that river-bed those who get the permission under section 11 of the act then such river-bed is obstructed due to the cultivator and the path will divert the river-bed the conservator has the power to stop cultivation on that river-bed . The cultivator needs to obey the order of the conservator of the district if he fails to do so and disobey the order of the conservator then will be liable to pay a fine of rupees five hundred on conviction before magistrate and then he not paid the said fine amount he will send to simple imprisonment for a period of three months.⁴⁴

3.1.3 Construction on River-Bed Without Permission

The construction, plantation in the river-bed without permission is prohibited. The land is surveyed and notified as a river-bed then anyone who wishes to make any construction or plantation on the said area to newly make any plantation or construction or to extend any construction, plantation or to remove any plantation, construction of any kinds or trees, grasses needs to give an application in writing before one month to the conservator to seek permission for licence to do the construction or plantation or tress or grass in that river-bed. Plantation for the purpose of this act means not only a thing which is plug in a year or twice plantation also includes the growing of the plants for the purpose of cutting, shoot, seedlings such as betel leaves, sugarcane, bamboo. The conservator of the river after receiving the application by the

occupier or cultivator on that river-bed he may grant or deny the application with orders in writing. The conservator after the expiry period of the one month he has not pass any orders then it is free to the applicant to make the said changes in the application without any instruction to the conservator of the river.⁴⁵ The applicant who received an order from the conservator has not fulfilled with the order of the conservator then he may appeal the order of the conservator to the concerned collector of that district with sixty days to receive of copy of the order.⁴⁶ The particulars of the appeal should be in a concise form stating the objection of the said order of the conservator then the district collector need to hear that appeal and dispose of it. Those who not follow the provisions of this section will be punished with fine of rupees one thousand and if he fails to pay then he will go to simple imprisonment for a period of six months for every such offences.⁴⁷

The conservator has the power with prior sanction from the collector of the district in writing then he has the power to direct the cultivator or occupier of the land in the said river-bed to remove the construction or plantation or tree or grass or any other things which is on the said land is an obstruction for the route course of the stream of the river and it shall be the duty of the occupier to comply with the orders of the conservator within the period of time. In this case if a order is made to remove any building then the occupier is free to make an appeal on that order through the collector of district against that order to the board of revenue after receiving the receipt of the copy of the order within sixty days of that date in this case the order will be stopped till the order decided by the board of the revenue. In this appeal, every appeal and order of the said will be send along with a copy to the conservator of the river.⁴⁸ The occupier who is failed to comply with the order will be punished of rupees one thousand rupees and if he fails to pay, he will go to simple imprisonment for a period of six months for every such offences.⁴⁹

All particulars and copies will be submitted to the district collector by the conservator of the river. The section 11 and 13 of this act the writing about the extent of the cultivation, nature of the cultivation or thing need to be sent. It shall be the duty of the conservator to record every such extent in the survey register and in the certified copies to the possession of the collector. Under section 12 and 14 the conservator made any order it is the duty of the conservator to produce the copy to the district collector of the said district.⁵⁰

Compensation to the Occupier

Under section 11,12,13,14 the conservator of the river refuses to give permission to the occupier for plantation, cultivate , build any construction or the conservator order to demolish any construction or plantation in that river-bed or any other obstruction during the time of the survey then the owner or occupier is eligible to get compensation for the refusal or demolish of his plantation or cultivation.⁵¹

Power of the Conservator

The conservator has the power to do some necessary act to prevent danger to life or property. The conservator of the river is wholesome responsible to the river and if any danger or harm which causes the obstruction in the river-bed or overflow in the river then the conservator has all the powers to be necessary to prevent erosion, breach of embankments or the flooding over them, encroachments by the stream or danger to life or property for this purpose notwithstanding anything in the said act he has some discretionary powers to entry in to public as well as private land and the land is within the river-bed or outside of it and the conservator can dig it and use the surface of the earth and he construct , grow , grass or shrubs on the place or remove and cut the grass , plant in that place to alter the course of any stream. The conservator needs to give a detailed report regarding every act done by him under this section and the occupier of the lands gets compensation.⁵²

The conservator may delegate all or one of his powers to his subordinate who was nominated by himself and the person who is nominated the conservator need to put it on the said district official gazette.

The conservator is deemed to be the officers of the in charge of river under central act 1 of 1858. In the case of default by the occupier to remove the obstruction after the order of removal by the conservator then the conservator he may himself remove the obstruction and whatever the expense happened due to the removal of the obstruction the conservator will file the expenses to the district collector and then the expense will recover from the owner or occupier of the land through arrears of land revenue.⁵³

The person who obstructs the conservator to not done his duty which is given to him under this act then the person shall be deemed to have commit the offence of section 186 of the code.⁵⁴

Power to Make Rules

The state government for their convenience may make rules in this act and the state government will alter, add and repeal rules which is inconsistent with this act for the work of any injury while doing construction or create any damage to the conservator of the river and if any one who is disobey the rules made under this act will be punished with rupee not more than fifty. Every such rules must be published in the official gazette for the upcoming three consecutive issues and needs to published in the district where the river is situated the rules which framed under this act will come to operation only after the publication of the one month expiry period.⁵⁵ The conservator who is appointed is to be a public servant under this act.⁵⁶ The fines which is put under this act will be recovered in the manner of code of criminal procedure code.⁵⁷

Period of Limitation

The period of limitation for the suit against conservator. No suit will initiate against conservator , surveyor or their subordinates who appointed under this act for any official thing is done under this act without sending notice . No evidence of cause of action expect that stated in notice will taken against the conservator after the expiry period of three months shall be in writing and given to the conservator or surveyor or subordinates or person at his place in that they need to put the name and office of the plaintiff and agent if any and while the suit is initiated the plaintiff will only go with the evidence which is stated by him in the notice and he will not permit to produce any further evidence and unless the notice is proved the court shall find for the defendant and every suit must be commence within the six month of the cause of action.⁵⁸

Conclusion:

The movement of remote people to urban for various activities and for the betterment of their livelihood the people started encroaching the places and the government agencies which have the provisions of converting the water bodies which was not in use and extinct due to extensive drought, the agencies converting the waterbodies to building for the welfare of the people. Due to the illegal encroachment and legal sanction of waterbodies to industries and other infrastructure projects the waterbodies are getting endangered one. The wetlands which need to be protected but it was converted to building legally by the authorities. The study aims to

repeal the provision of destroying the water bodies due to its no-use and converting the waterbodies in to building, rather than giving permission for converting the waterbodies into building for social welfare, the state needs to repeal the provision and state needs to develop, clean and take action for protection the waterbodies which are in the state of extinction.

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⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Wetland and ecosystem services, available at: <https://www.cbd.int/waters/doc/wwd2015/wwd-2015-press-briefs-en.pdf> (last visited on 16/04/2026).

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⁸ Ibid.

⁹ Water Pollution, available at: <https://earthjournalism.net/resources/water-pollution> (last visited on 16/04/2026).

¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹ Encroachment, available at: https://dec.vermont.gov/sites/dec/files/documents/wsmd_swms_StressorPlan_Encroachment.pdf (last visited on 18/04/2024).

¹² Ajith Athardy, 9.45 lakh water bodies identified in country, 18,691 encroached upon: Jal Shakti ministry, available at: <https://www.deccanherald.com/national/945-lakh-water-bodies-identified-in-country-18691-encroached-upon-jal-shakti-ministry-1091155.html> (last visited on 26/06/2022).

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¹⁴ The Constitution of India, Arts. 48-A, 51A(g).

¹⁵ The Constitution of India, Art. 223.

¹⁶ The Constitution Of India, Schedule 7, List 1, Entry 56.

¹⁷ The Constitution Of India, Schedule 7, List 2, Entry17.

¹⁸ The Constitution Of India, Art. 21.

¹⁹ M.P. Jain, Indian Constitutional Law 1169 (LexisNexis, Haryana, 8th edn., 2018).

²⁰ Dr. Paramjit S. Jaswal, Dr. Nishtha Jaswal, Environmental Law 52 (Allahabad Law Agency, Haryana, 4th edn., 2020).

²¹ L.K. Koolwal v. State of Rajasthan , AIR 1988 Raj 2.

²² World population review, <https://worldpopulationreview.com/world-cities/jaipur-population> (last visited on 29-05-2022).

²³ L.K. Koolwal v. State of Rajasthan , AIR 1988 Raj 2.

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ Subash Kumar v. State of Bihar , AIR 1991 520.

²⁷ Ibid.

²⁸ Ibid.

²⁹ Even if god encroaches upon the public land court will order removal, Madras High Court, available at: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/chennai/even-if-god-encroaches-upon-public-land-court-will-order-removal-madras-high-court/articleshow/90453007.cms> (last visited on June 19, 2022).

³⁰ Tamil Nadu river conservancy act , 1884 (Act 6 of 1884), Available at: [https://www.informea.org/en/legislation/tamil-nadu-rivers-conservancy-act-1884-no-6-1884#:~:text=6%20of%201884\),,-](https://www.informea.org/en/legislation/tamil-nadu-rivers-conservancy-act-1884-no-6-1884#:~:text=6%20of%201884),,-)

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³¹ Ibid.

³² Tamil Nadu Adaption of Laws Order , 1970 (Notification No. Part 4-Section 4 of the Fort St, George Gazette Extraordinary, dated the 10th January 1970), The Schedule , Tamil Nadu Regulations.

³³ Madras Rivers Conservancy (Amendment) Act, 1942 (Madras Act XXI of 1942).

³⁴ Madras Rivers Conservancy (Amendment) Act, 1949 (Madras Act XXXI of 1949).

³⁵ Tamil Nadu river conservancy act , 1884 (Act 6 of 1884) ss.3,4.

³⁶ Land Acquisition act , 1870 (Act 10 of 1870) (Repealed) , section -4 : Power to entry and survey , Section - 5: Payment for damages.

³⁷ Tamil Nadu river conservancy act , 1884 (Act 6 of 1884) , s.5.

³⁸ Ibid.

³⁹ Tamil Nadu river conservancy act , 1884 (Act 6 of 1884), s.6.

⁴⁰ Id., s.7.

⁴¹ Id, ss.8,9.

⁴² Tamil Nadu river conservancy act , 1884 (Act 6 of 1884)s.11.

⁴³ Id.,s.11.

⁴⁴ Id.,s.12.

⁴⁵ Tamil Nadu river conservancy act , 1884 (Act 6 of 1884)s.13.

⁴⁶ Ibid.

⁴⁷ Ibid,

⁴⁸ Tamil Nadu river conservancy act , 1884 (Act 6 of 1884)s.14.

⁴⁹ Ibid.

⁵⁰ Tamil Nadu river conservancy act , 1884 (Act 6 of 1884)s.15.

⁵¹ Ibid.

⁵² Tamil Nadu river conservancy act , 1884 (Act 6 of 1884)ss.16,17,18,19,20,21.

⁵³ Ibid.

⁵⁴ Indian penal code , 1860 (Act XLV of 1860)S.186- Obstructing public servant in discharge of public functions.—Whoever voluntarily obstructs any public servant in the discharge of his public functions, shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to three months, or with fine which may extend to five hundred rupees, or with both.

⁵⁵ Tamil Nadu river conservancy act , 1884 (Act 6 of 1884)s.22.

⁵⁶ Id.,s.23.

⁵⁷ Id.,s.24.

⁵⁸ Id.,ss.25,26.